

qilaveradi. Hatto dadasining o'ziga qarata ham huddi shunday ishora qila boshlaydi. Xuddi shunday bolalarning ma'naviy kamolotga yetishida masal janrining ham o'ziga xos o'rni bor.

Masal – majozga asoslangan voqeaband kichik she'r. Bunda jonsiz narsa-hodisalar, qush, hayvon va parrandalar insonga xos xarakter-xususiyatlarni namoyon etadi. Masalan, "Tulki ila qarg'a", "Tuya bilan bo'taloq", "Sher bilan durroj". Masal janrining otasi sifatida dunyo adabiyotida Ezop tan olinadi.

Ezop – asli Frigiya, qul qilib sotilgan, xunuk bir donishmand, 500 ga yaqin masallari bor. Ezop uzoq yo'lga chiqqanda nonli qutini ko'taradi, yo'l yurilgani sayin non yeyilib Ezopning yuki engil bo'lib boradi. Ezop dengizni ichib bilaman deb garov o'ynagan xo'jayinini qutqaradi, ammo qul bo'lib qolaveradi. "Yovvoyi echkilar bilan cho'pon" masalida yangi do'stni eski do'stdan afzal biladiganlar bilan do'stlashishga shoshilmang deyilgan. "Kiyik bilan tokzor" masalida yaxshilik qilganga yomonlik qilgan xudo g'azabiga uchraydi deyilgan. Yaxshilik qilganga yaxshilik qilish lozim deyilgan. "Bo'ri bilan laylak" masalida ayrim badfe'l kishilar yomonlik qilmaganlarini yaxshilik qilganlari deb biladilar. Masalda yaxshilikni qadrlaganga yaxshilik qil deyilgan. "Eshak bilan baqalar" masalida "Birni ko'rib fikr qil, birni ko'rib shukr qil" degan fikr bor, ayrim kishilar ozgina qiyinchilikdan esankiraydilar, ayrimlar og'ir qiyinchiliklarni sabr bilan yengadilar. "Ustiga tuz yuklangan eshak" masalidan xulosa shuki, ayrimlar ishlatgan hiyla nayrang ularning o'z boshiga yetarkan. "Og'irning ustidan, engilning ustidan o'tma" deydi xalqimiz, "Behuda chiranish belni chiqaradi". "Burgut, zag'cha va cho'pon" masalida "Ko'rpangga qarab oyoq uzat" deyilgan. Birinchi masalchi Ezop, so'ng Fedr. Mashhur masalchilar: Lafonten, Lessing, Gellert, Krilov, o'zbeklarda A.Navoiy, Gulxaniy, Avloniy, Hamza, Yamin Qurbon, S.Abdiqahhor, M.Xudoyqulov.

Biz aynan boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga o'rgatish mumkin bo'lgan masallarni tahlilga tortib, M Xudoyqulovning o'zbek bolalar masachiligiga qo'shgan hissasini ta'kidlashni istadik. "Qizilishton bilan qurt" masaliga diqqat qiling:

Qizilishton qurt tushgan daraxtga qo'nib, tumshug'i bilan taqillata boshladi.

– Kim kerak? – dedi Qurt ichkaridan.

– Daraxtni kemirib yotgan zararkunanda kerak. Bu yoqqa chiqsin, ishim bor, – dedi Qizilishton.

Qurt kavagiga ming berkinsin – bekor...

Bu masal yordamida bolalarga "Zararli ishlar bilan shug'ullangan inson qurtga o'xshaydi. Noto'g'ri ish qilishdan to'xtamasa, kavakka yashirinsa ham jazo olgan qurtga o'xshab qoladi", – deya tarbiya berish mumkin.

M Xudoyqulovning qator masallarida sarlavha yechim yoki tugunni yuzaga keltiradi. Oqibat masal syujeti sarlavhasiz kemptik bo'lib qoladi. Bunday usul Anvar Obidjon she'rlarida uchraydi. Ko'rinadiki, sarlavhaning syujet uchun juda muhimligini ta'minlash ham mahorat.

M Xudoyqulov "Yoshlarga o'g'it", "Hadikchi", "Sinchalakning himmati", "Manzara", "Qismat" kabi masallarida shunday yo'l tutgan.

M. Xudoyqulovning bolalarbop masallariga xos xususiyatlardan yana biri shundaki, xalq maqollarining ma'lum qismi yoki matal sarlavha vazifasini o'taydi va oddiy folklorizm yuzaga keladi. "Ayrilganni ayiq yer", "Sabr tubi – sariq oltin", "Shoshgan qiz...", "Qazisan qartasan...", "Andishaning oti qo'rqqoqmi?" kabi masallar fikrimizni dalillaydi. Aytaylik, "Birlashgan o'zar" masali bor-yo'g'i uch jumladan iborat: "Qum sochilib yotardi. Uni sement bilan birlashtirishdi. Endi ularni na o't ajrata olardi, na suv..." Masalnavisning xulosasi sarlavhada aks etgan. Sement bilan qum birlashgani uchun ular mustahkam bo'ldi. Masalni o'qigan bolalar qum bilan sement aralashtirilsa, qorib beton hosil qilinishini o'rganadi. Agar bilsa, betonning qattiqligini anglaydi. Ayni damda, maqolning ikkinchi qismini topib o'rganadi: "Birlashgan o'zar – birlashmagan to'zar". Ushbu maqol va masal yordamida o'qituvchi o'quvchini birlikka o'rgatadi.

M. Xudoyqulovning bolalarbop masallariga xos xususiyatlardan yana biri shundaki, xalq maqollarining ma'lum qismi yoki matal sarlavha vazifasini o'taydi va oddiy folklorizm yuzaga keladi. "Ayrilganni ayiq yer", "Sabr tubi – sariq oltin", "Shoshgan qiz...", "Qazisan qartasan...",

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ANALYTICAL METHODS OF PROVERBS IN CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Abstract: *In this article, the forms of proverbs in children's literature, their appearance, principles of development, laws, analytical methods are scientifically and theoretically analyzed.*

Key words: *qawl, naql, parable, paremiography, paremiology, istilah, irsol-ul masal, saj, rhyming, aphorism.*

Preschool and primary school age children have proverbs, proverbs, proverbs, sayings, sayings, sayings of wisdom, words of wisdom, rebuke, sayings of elders, sayings of sages or sages, sayings of poets and sayings of fathers. Examples of this genre, which are popular among people with the terms In the scientific method, the term proverb is used. The proverb is derived from the Arabic word "qawalla" and means "to tell, to adjust". Among the people, there are expressions "steady in speech" or "unsteady in speech": the first one means "steady in speech, single-minded", and the

second means "unsteady in speech, unable to overcome small speech, not having the same work with speech". Therefore, the word "proverb" in Uzbek language has two meanings, firstly, it means "speech, speech" in the literal sense, and secondly, it means a widespread genre in folklore.

It influenced the emergence of proverbs, parables, and narrative genres, and due to the fact that the conclusion of parables and parables became a part of the story, it was sometimes confused with the terms of parables and parables. In fact, the word "parable" is also Arabic and means "similar", but in Uzbek it has two meanings, like a proverb and a metaphorical story aimed at explaining a purpose. However, by the 20th century, its use in the proverbial sense was limited. Only in Tajik folklore it was decided to call a proverb with the term "parable".

Although the word "Naql" remains in the proverbial sense, it is an Arabic word that means "to copy". In the Uzbek language, it has a secondary meaning like "narrate, tell a story, narrate" and remains as a scientific term representing an independent aphoristic genre of folk oral prose. In the proverb "A good saying is the root of the mind" is the meaning of "saying".

Proverbs are a widespread independent genre of oral artistic creativity as rare examples of folk wisdom. Conditionally, they can be called the rules of public etiquette. After all, proverbs are a phenomenon born from the very concise, concise, concise and figurative expression of the social-political, spiritual-cultural, moral-philosophical views of the people tested in their life experiences over the centuries. Proverbs are not specially created, but arise as a judgment as a moral assessment of the conclusion born from life experience tested due to the requirements of a certain situation. Although each nation's proverbs express the heart and national views of that nation, the meaning in them belongs to the whole nation. Due to these features, proverbs have acquired national and universal essence.

Proverbs were created in the form of a stable and unchanging, correct and truthful summary of the long-term life experiences of people in the course of their activities in various fields. Proverbs are in both poetic and prose forms, neither lyrical nor epic. For this reason, they, like riddles, idioms and figurative expressions, are included in the paremic type, and their recording and collection and reading pertains to paremiography, while their appearance, principles and laws of development, and art are organized in paremiology.

In proverbs, sayings are active, creating a unique inner rhyme and ensuring their harmony. There are different ways of classifying proverbs. In particular, grouping or classification according to alphabetical order, topics, synonymous or antonymic essence, literal or figurative meaning, and according to the social period in which it was created - chronology has become a tradition in paremiology. But so far, in Uzbek proverbs, the pineapple of alphabetical order and classification according to the topic has been followed in the compilation of the two-volume Uzbek folk proverbs (1987) and the multi-volume collection of Uzbek folk proverbs (1989) under the column "Uzbek folk art". Nevertheless, it can be observed that the history of recording Uzbek folk proverbs is very old and continued in two directions:

The first step is to record and read proverbs from the people as they are said in the live setting. The first recording and reading of Uzbek folk proverbs is associated with the name of Mahmud Kashgari, a great philologist of the 11th century. He was among many Turkic tribes and peoples, among other examples of folk art, he recorded many proverbs and published them in the work "Devonu Lugotit Turk", and on this basis he also started the practice of reading proverbs.

The practice of writing down Uzbek folk proverbs was continued by the poets Muhammadsharif Gulkhani and Sulaymongul Raji who lived and created in the end of the 18th century and the first half of the 19th century. Gulkhani found more than 400 folk proverbs, and Rojii 450, and collected them in their "Zarbulmasal". Of course, they did not collect proverbs for scientific purposes. In this, they mainly intended to strengthen folk appeal in their works, to individualize the language of the characters, and to achieve natural, simple expressiveness. Nevertheless, this service of theirs is particularly important in showing the historical progress of Uzbek paremiography.